

Childhood height growth rate association with the risk of islet autoimmunity and development of type 1 diabetes

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Online-only Supplemental Material

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Supplement 1: The T1DI Study Group

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Supplemental Figure S1: Study cohort selection flowchart. IAA indicates insulin autoantibodies; GADA, glutamic acid decarboxylase autoantibodies; and IA-2A, insulinoma-associated antigen-2 autoantibodies.

Supplement 2: Modeling of growth curves and missing value imputation using linear mixed effects model

To model the growth trajectories of height and weight over time and impute the missing values, linear mixed effects models (LMEM) were fit to the growth measures of subjects in the cohort. LMEMs can be used to estimate the mean growth curves by study center (fixed effects), and for each individual subject, generate best linear unbiased predictors (BLUPs) for height and weight separately (random effects). Therefore, LMEMs can be used for imputing the missing values in the growth features. To fit LMEM to the growth period, first we plotted the observed growth measures of individual subjects at the clinical visits. Next, mixed effects models with the best-fitting polynomials were fit to the childhood growth period. LMEM used the height (or weight) as the outcome, age and quadratic age as the fixed effects, with random intercepts and slopes, adjusting for sex, and study site. At each visit with measurements or missing data, BLUPs of individual subjects' growth trajectories were assessed. Moreover, the first derivatives of the polynomials used in LMEM gave the BLUPs of instantaneous growth rates. According to Akaike information criteria (AIC), second order polynomials in both the fixed and random effects were used for modeling the height and weight trajectories. Plots of the growth trajectories using raw measurements and fitted BLUP curves were similar.

Supplemental Figure S2: Plots of raw growth measurements by study site. Left: height (cm); Right: weight(kg). The X-axis represents age of 1 – 8 years.

Supplemental Figure S3: Plots of fitted growth measurements (height and weight) by study site using linear mixed effects models. Left: height (cm); Right: weight(kg). The X-axis represents age of 1 – 8 years.

Supplement 3: Missing autoantibody status information imputation

Missing autoantibody status information was imputed by autoantibody type according to the following rules in order of priority:

Rule 1: For visits with missing autoantibody status within 3 months of a visit with known status, we filled in the missing data points with the available status.

Rule 2: if the visit with missing data point(s) is bracketed by visits with available statuses:

- If all available autoantibody statuses are negative, then all missing data points between available statuses were imputed to be negative.
- If the available autoantibody statuses are negative for sequential visits, but convert to positive at some visit, then all missing data points between the negative and the positive statuses, were imputed to be negative.
- If all available autoantibody statuses are positive, then all missing data points between available statuses were imputed to be positive.
- If the available autoantibody statuses are positive for sequential visits, but then convert to negative at some visit, then all missing data points between the positive and negative statuses, were imputed to be negative.

Rule 3: The missing data points should be imputed to be negative if the visits following it all have negative statuses.

Supplementary Table 1. Key characteristics of the study cohort for one year of age to seroconversion with any of IAA, GADA or IA-2A: Model 1(A)

Characteristics	All (n=10,008)	Developed Seroconversion (n=592)	Did Not Develop Seroconversion (n=9,416)
Male Sex (n (%))	4,670 (46.7)	262 (44.3)	4,408 (46.8)
<i>Study site (n (%))</i>			
DAISY	1,338 (13.4)	75 (12.7)	1,263 (13.4)
DIPIS	1,229 (12.3)	73 (12.3)	1,156 (12.3)
DIPP	6,133 (61.3)	367 (62.0)	5,766 (61.2)
BABYDIAB	1,308 (13.1)	77 (13.0)	1,231 (13.1)
<i>HLA Risk Group (n (%))</i>			
A	1,335 (13.3)	137 (23.1)	1,198 (12.7)
B	4,878 (48.7)	276 (46.6)	4,602 (48.9)
C	1,518 (15.2)	72 (12.2)	1,446 (15.4)
D	2,277 (22.8)	107 (18.1)	2,170 (23.0)
Duration of follow-up in years (mean (SD))	6.95 (1.60)	6.98 (1.46)	6.95 (1.61)
<i>Number of growth measures available per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	8.09 (5.02)	12.03 (6.69)	7.84 (4.78)
Weight (mean (SD))	8.21 (4.98)	12.17 (6.66)	7.96 (4.74)
<i>Number of imputed growth measures per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	1.23 (1.93)	2.07 (3.06)	1.18 (1.82)
Weight (mean (SD))	1.12 (1.94)	1.93 (3.06)	1.07 (1.84)

Supplementary Table 2. Key characteristics of the study cohort for one year of age to seroconversion with IAA: Model 1(B)

Characteristics	All (n=10,045)	Developed Persistent IAA (n=361)	Did Not Develop Persistent IAA (n=9,684)
Male Sex (n (%))	4,688 (46.7)	151 (41.8)	4,537 (46.9)
<i>Study site (n (%))</i>			
DAISY	1,345 (13.4)	49 (13.6)	1,296 (13.4)
DIPIS	1,232 (12.3)	22 (6.1)	1,210 (12.5)
DIPP	6,156 (61.3)	238 (65.9)	5,918 (61.1)
BABYDIAB	1,312 (13.1)	52 (14.4)	1,260 (13.0)
<i>HLA Risk Group (n (%))</i>			
A	1,340 (13.3)	84 (23.3)	1,256 (13.0)
B	4,893 (48.7)	177 (49.0)	4,716 (48.7)
C	1,528 (15.2)	44 (12.2)	1,484 (15.3)
D	2,284 (22.7)	56 (15.5)	2,228 (23.0)
<i>Duration of follow-up in years (mean (SD))</i>	6.95 (1.60)	6.69 (1.73)	6.96 (1.59)
<i>Number of growth measures available per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	8.10 (5.02)	12.78 (7.04)	7.93 (4.84)
Weight (mean (SD))	8.22 (4.98)	12.95 (7.00)	8.04 (4.80)
<i>Number of imputed growth measures per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	1.23 (1.93)	1.96 (3.02)	1.21 (1.87)
Weight (mean (SD))	1.12 (1.95)	1.79 (3.01)	1.09 (1.89)

Supplementary Table 3. Key characteristics of the study cohort for one year of age to seroconversion with GADA: Model 1(C)

Characteristics	All (n=10,085)	Developed Persistent GADA (n=458)	Did Not Develop Persistent GADA (n=9,627)
Male Sex (n (%))	4,704 (46.6)	207 (45.2)	4,497 (46.7)
<i>Study site (n (%))</i>			
DAISY	1,360 (13.5)	59 (12.9)	1,301 (13.5)
DIPIS	1,229 (12.2)	60 (13.1)	1,169 (12.1)
DIPP	6,182 (61.3)	282 (61.6)	5,900 (61.3)
BABYDIAB	1,314 (13.0)	57 (12.4)	1,257 (13.1)
<i>HLA Risk Group (n (%))</i>			
A	1,352 (13.4)	120 (26.2)	1,232 (12.8)
B	4,920 (48.8)	206 (45.0)	4,714 (49.0)
C	1,523 (15.1)	49 (10.7)	1,474 (15.3)
D	2,290 (22.7)	83 (18.1)	2,207 (22.9)
Duration of follow-up in years (mean (SD))	6.94 (1.61)	6.90 (1.58)	6.95 (1.61)
<i>Number of growth measures available per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	8.11 (5.03)	12.45 (7.02)	7.90 (4.82)
Weight (mean (SD))	8.23 (5.00)	12.58 (7.00)	8.02 (4.78)
<i>Number of imputed growth measures per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	1.24 (1.94)	2.20 (3.22)	1.19 (1.84)
Weight (mean (SD))	1.12 (1.95)	2.06 (3.22)	1.07 (1.86)

Supplementary Table 4. Key characteristics of the study cohort for one year of age to seroconversion with multiple autoantibodies: Model 1(D)

Characteristics	All (n=10,070)	Developed Seroconversion with Multiple Autoantibodies (n=359)	Did Not Develop Seroconversion with Multiple Autoantibodies (n=9,711)
Male Sex (n (%))	4,704 (46.7)	168 (46.8)	4,536 (46.7)
<i>Study site (n (%))</i>			
DAISY	1,352 (13.4)	41 (11.4)	1,311 (13.5)
DIPIS	1,230 (12.2)	45 (12.5)	1,185 (12.2)
DIPP	6,176 (61.3)	226 (63)	5,950 (61.3)
BABYDIAB	1,312 (13.0)	47 (13.1)	1,265 (13.0)
<i>HLA Risk Group (n (%))</i>			
A	1,344 (13.3)	103 (28.7)	1,241 (12.8)
B	4,910 (48.8)	174 (48.5)	4,736 (48.8)
C	1,526 (15.2)	32 (8.9)	1,494 (15.4)
D	2,290 (22.7)	50 (13.9)	2,240 (23.1)
Duration of follow-up in years (mean (SD))	6.95 (1.60)	6.69 (1.70)	6.96 (1.60)
<i>Number of growth measures available per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	8.11 (5.03)	13.13 (7.21)	7.92 (4.83)
Weight (mean (SD))	8.22 (4.99)	13.26 (7.17)	8.04 (4.79)
<i>Number of imputed growth measures per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	1.24 (1.93)	2.32 (3.45)	1.20 (1.84)
Weight (mean (SD))	1.12 (1.95)	2.19 (3.42)	1.08 (1.86)

Supplementary Table 5. Key characteristics of the study cohort for one year of age to type 1 diabetes diagnosis: Model 2

Characteristics	All (n=10,144)	Developed Diabetes (n=131)	Did Not Develop Diabetes (n=10,013)
Male Sex (n (%))	4,732 (46.6)	61 (46.6)	4,671 (46.6)
<i>Study site (n (%))</i>			
DAISY	1,373 (13.5)	25 (19.1)	1,348 (13.5)
DIPIS	1,233 (12.2)	18 (13.7)	1,215 (12.1)
DIPP	6,215 (61.3)	64 (48.9)	6,151 (61.4)
BABYDIAB	1,323 (13.0)	24 (18.3)	1,299 (13.0)
<i>HLA Risk Group (n (%))</i>			
A	1,368 (13.5)	57 (43.5)	1,311 (13.1)
B	4,941 (48.7)	44 (33.6)	4,897 (48.9)
C	1,535 (15.1)	13 (9.9)	1,522 (15.2)
D	2,300 (22.7)	17 (13.0)	2,283 (22.8)
<i>Duration of follow-up in years (mean (SD))</i>	6.94 (1.61)	5.06 (1.85)	6.96 (1.60)
<i>Number of growth measures available per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	8.12 (5.05)	9.44 (5.74)	8.11 (5.03)
Weight (mean (SD))	8.24 (5.01)	9.78 (5.70)	8.22 (5.00)
<i>Number of imputed growth measures per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	1.24 (1.95)	2.80 (3.32)	1.22 (1.92)
Weight (mean (SD))	1.13 (1.96)	2.46 (3.26)	1.11 (1.93)

Supplementary Table 6. Key characteristics of the study cohort for seroconversion with any of IAA, GADA or IA-2A to type 1 diabetes diagnosis: Model 3(A)

Characteristics	All (n=720)	Developed Diabetes (n=92)	Did Not Develop Diabetes (n=628)
Male Sex (n (%))	320 (44.4)	46 (50.0)	274 (43.6)
<i>Study site (n (%))</i>			
DAISY	110 (15.3)	23 (25.0)	87 (13.9)
DIPIS	77 (10.7)	18 (19.6)	59 (9.4)
DIPP	440 (61.1)	34 (37.0)	406 (64.6)
BABYDIAB	93 (12.9)	17 (18.5)	76 (12.1)
<i>HLA Risk Group (n (%))</i>			
A	169 (23.5)	40 (43.5)	129 (20.5)
B	335 (46.5)	30 (32.6)	305 (48.6)
C	86 (11.9)	7 (7.6)	79 (12.6)
D	130 (18.1)	15 (16.3)	115 (18.3)
Duration of follow-up in years (mean (SD))	3.60 (1.98)	3.28 (1.68)	3.64 (2.01)
<i>Number of growth measures available per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	8.52 (6.46)	7.29 (4.69)	8.70 (6.67)
Weight (mean (SD))	8.60 (6.47)	7.63 (4.75)	8.75 (6.68)
<i>Number of imputed growth measures per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	1.49 (2.48)	3.20 (3.25)	1.25 (2.25)
Weight (mean (SD))	1.41 (2.43)	2.86 (3.25)	1.20 (2.21)

Supplementary Table 7. Key characteristics of the study cohort for seroconversion with IAA to type 1 diabetes diagnosis: Model 3(B)

Characteristics	All (n=458)	Developed Diabetes (n=77)	Did Not Develop Diabetes (n=381)
Male Sex (n (%))	193 (42.1)	39 (50.6)	154 (40.4)
<i>Study site (n (%))</i>			
DAISY	77 (16.8)	23 (29.9)	54 (14.2)
DIPIS	23 (5.0)	5 (6.5)	18 (4.7)
DIPP	294 (64.2)	34 (44.2)	260 (68.2)
BABYDIAB	64 (14.0)	15 (19.5)	49 (12.9)
<i>HLA Risk Group (n (%))</i>			
A	112 (24.5)	30 (39.0)	82 (21.5)
B	224 (48.9)	27 (35.1)	197 (51.7)
C	50 (10.9)	7 (9.1)	43 (11.3)
D	72 (15.7)	13 (16.9)	59 (15.5)
Duration of follow-up in years (mean (SD))	3.65 (2.09)	3.07 (1.79)	3.77 (2.13)
<i>Number of growth measures available per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	9.14 (6.77)	7.12 (4.77)	9.55 (7.04)
Weight (mean (SD))	9.24 (6.77)	7.43 (4.81)	9.61 (7.05)
<i>Number of imputed growth measures per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	1.43 (2.36)	2.71 (3.23)	1.18 (2.06)
Weight (mean (SD))	1.33 (2.30)	2.40 (3.22)	1.12 (2.01)

Supplementary Table 8. Key characteristics of the study cohort for seroconversion with GADA to type 1 diabetes diagnosis: Model 3(C)

Characteristics	All (n=508)	Developed Diabetes (n=70)	Did Not Develop Diabetes (n=438)
Male Sex (n (%))	231 (45.5)	39 (55.7)	192 (43.8)
<i>Study site (n (%))</i>			
DAISY	72 (14.2)	14 (20.0)	58 (13.2)
DIPIS	64 (12.6)	15 (21.4)	49 (11.2)
DIPP	305 (60.0)	25 (35.7)	280 (63.9)
BABYDIAB	67 (13.2)	16 (22.9)	51 (11.6)
<i>HLA Risk Group (n (%))</i>			
A	136 (26.8)	31 (44.3)	105 (24.0)
B	221 (43.5)	21 (30.0)	200 (45.7)
C	58 (11.4)	6 (8.6)	52 (11.9)
D	93 (18.3)	12 (17.1)	81 (18.5)
Duration of follow-up in years (mean (SD))	3.40 (1.85)	3.17 (1.62)	3.44 (1.89)
<i>Number of growth measures available per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	8.52 (6.57)	7.04 (4.89)	8.75 (6.77)
Weight (mean (SD))	8.58 (6.58)	7.27 (4.92)	8.79 (6.79)
<i>Number of imputed growth measures per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	1.58 (2.55)	3.29 (3.40)	1.31 (2.28)
Weight (mean (SD))	1.52 (2.50)	3.06 (3.39)	1.27 (2.24)

Supplementary Table 9. Key characteristics of the study cohort for seroconversion with multiple autoantibodies to type 1 diabetes diagnosis: Model 3(D)

Characteristics	All (n=428)	Developed Diabetes (n=92)	Did Not Develop Diabetes (n=336)
Male Sex (n (%))	193 (45.1)	44 (47.8)	149 (44.3)
<i>Study site (n (%))</i>			
DAISY	62 (14.5)	21 (22.8)	41 (12.2)
DIPIS	48 (11.2)	18 (19.6)	30 (8.9)
DIPP	259 (60.5)	36 (39.1)	223 (66.4)
BABYDIAB	59 (13.8)	17 (18.5)	42 (12.5)
<i>HLA Risk Group (n (%))</i>			
A	126 (29.4)	39 (42.4)	87 (25.9)
B	203 (47.4)	31 (33.7)	172 (51.2)
C	39 (9.1)	7 (7.6)	32 (9.5)
D	60 (14)	15 (16.3)	45 (13.4)
Duration of follow-up in years (mean (SD))	3.45 (1.90)	3.25 (1.72)	3.50 (1.94)
<i>Number of growth measures available per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	9.27 (6.83)	7.41 (5.18)	9.78 (7.13)
Weight (mean (SD))	9.37 (6.83)	7.72 (5.21)	9.83 (7.15)
<i>Number of imputed growth measures per subject</i>			
Height (mean (SD))	1.76 (2.83)	3.08 (3.26)	1.40 (2.59)
Weight (mean (SD))	1.66 (2.76)	2.77 (3.25)	1.36 (2.54)